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Research Article

**A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY OF BIOPSYCHOSOCIAL
EFFECTS OF MOBILE PHONES ON THE STUDENTS OF
DIFFERENT INSTITUTES OF LAHORE, PAKISTAN****¹Dr. Muhammad Usman Ahmed Kamal, ²Dr. Aneeza Sikander, ³Dr. Usman Akhtar**¹ House Officer, Jinnah Hospital Lahore² Mayo Hospital Lahore³ Medical Officer, DHQ Hospital Mandi Bahauddin**Article Received:** May 2020**Accepted:** June 2020**Published:** July 2020**Abstract:**

Background: Mobile phone addiction is on the rise. It is a behavioral addiction thought to be similar to that of an Internet, gambling, shopping, or video game addiction and leads to severe impairment or distress in one's life

Objective: To understand the impact of mobile phones on youth. To analyze such agonizing moments, they faced and make remedies in that regard to reduce their level of distress.

Material and Methods: Cross-sectional study. Online survey of students in different study institutes of Lahore, Pakistan. 4 weeks (May 2020)

Inclusion criteria: We included only the students of different institutes who have been using mobile phones for a while. No one other than student community was included.

Exclusion criteria: (1). Anyone other than students. (2). College/Institute staff.

Data Collection and analysis: An online survey was conducted in different institutes of Lahore in which 260 students participated. Analysis was made via SPSS 21.

Results: 260 students participated. They ranged from age 15 to 25 above with those in between 22-25 years dominating the figure with a percentage of 55.8%. More than 50% students used this as an excuse for not getting involved in conversations. Most of the students thought that kids under 9 years of age should not be allowed to engage in the use of these smart devices and about 72% wanted to restrict their daily phone usage to less than 2 hours a day.

Conclusion: Mobile phones addiction in modern era is real. The survey concluded that mobile phones no doubt, are a huge source of education, communication, personal assistance and made many of us well organized but they have been a cause of distress. Thus, their use should be regularized accordingly, especially in the youngsters.

Key Words: Mobile phones, Impact on Youth.

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INTRODUCTION:

Psychological dependence is an emotional need for a substance or a drug that has no underlying physical needs and involves withdrawal symptoms (e.g. a state of unease and dissatisfaction) upon cessation of exposure to that substance or drug. In recent times, it has been classified as a form of addiction. In 2017, a cross cultural study was conducted in Europe that resulted in findings that dependence of mobile phones in young adults was greatly influenced by the frequency of mobile phones usage and specific applications of interest¹. Excessive use of internet led to development of mental disorders which affected the individuals emotionally². A review on mobile phones addiction concluded that the dependence varied by the pattern of their usage and mostly was for personal factors like self-esteem and attention seeking³.

A research on university students has shown that among the internet addicted, males were more prone and that was a factor behind their attitude and depressed behavior⁴. Excessive mobile phones usage had been found to be a psychological pathology⁵. Social media, SMSs and internet were the basic factors involved when the dependent person used mobile phones while dealing with other people⁶.

Overuse of mobile phones enforced poor sleep quality and quantity especially in young males⁷. And bedtime mobile phone usage was a predetermining factor in poor sleep⁸. Texting while driving was an impulsive and individualized approach⁹. A study in Iran concluded that frequency of mobile phones usage was increasing drastically among the children and that was not good in such age when nervous system developed¹⁰.

A research conducted on school students shown that, their short-term memory and reaction time was affected by radiofrequency radiations¹¹. According to a study, 31.33% of sample students shown dependence on mobile phones¹². Excessive use of cell phones and internet reported some somatic symptoms. Headache was found to be 28% of total sample with female preponderance¹³.

A research described that, 17.30%, 14.20% and 13.8% of university students were suffering from depressive disorder, obsessive compulsive disorder and interpersonal sensitivity respectively because of mobile phone addiction¹⁴. Poor sleep quality and duration was found to be related with overuse of social networks and smart phones¹⁵. British teenagers, studying in public schools were found to have mobile phone addiction symptoms¹⁶.

People suffering from panic disorder shown symptoms like anxiety, panic depression and perspiration related to mobile phone absence¹⁷. Road traffic accidents and crash risks were found to be minimized as a result of cell phone use restriction while driving¹⁸. Smart phone and internet overuse led to mobile phone induced ostracism and problems in interpersonal communication¹⁹.

A study reported that, iPod and texting dependence was found to be related with delayed discounting²⁰.

Objective:

The objectives included:

- To understand the impact of mobile phones on youth.
- To understand the biopsychosocial affects it has.
- To analyze such agonizing moments, they faced and make remedies in that regard to reduce their level of distress.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

STUDY DESIGN:

Cross sectional study

STUDY SETTING:

Online survey of students in different study institutes of Lahore, Pakistan.

DURATION OF STUDY:

4 weeks (May 2020)

SAMPLE SIZE:

Sample size was 260.

Confidence level was 95%.

Acceptable difference was 0.05%.

Assumed proportion was 0.05%.

SAMPLING TECHNIQUE:

Non-probability / purposive / convenient sampling via online survey analysis.

SAMPLE SELECTION:

Inclusion criteria: We included only the students of different institutes who have been using mobile phones for a while. No one other than student community was included.

Exclusion criteria: (1). Anyone other than students.
(2). College/Institute staff.

DATA COLLECTION PROCEDURE:

A cross-sectional study was conducted among a total of 260 subjects those fulfilled inclusion criteria. After an informed consent, detailed demographic information collected and each subject was delivered a questionnaire to fill

Each participant was informed of the nature of the

study beforehand. In addition, anonymity pertaining to the information they shared was ensured.

DATA ANALYSIS PROCEDURE:

Data was entered and analyzed in SPSS version 17.0 and frequency tables and percentages along with pie graphs were generated and likewise different variables e.g. age, sex, relation were calculated. Crosstabs were done for variables of interest and likewise histograms and bar graphs were generated.

RESULTS AND MAIN FINDINGS:

Phones being useful gadgets are also becoming an addiction for our youth. In order to evaluate the impact of these devices a survey was done in different institutes of Lahore, Pakistan.

260 students participated. They ranged from age 15 to 25 above with those in between 22-25 years dominating the figure with a percentage of 55.8 as shown in Bar chart (1). Around 60.4% students that is 157 out of 260 students had been using phones for more than 5 years as shown in Pie graph (1). While the average daily use was 3 to 5 hours, as in Bar chart (2). Entertainment was the main reason of consumption for about 100 students as shown in Frequency table (1), surpassing the votes for communication and education which clearly showed that its expected role in society is somewhat lost.

73.8% students felt uneasy without mobile phones, shown in Pie graph (2), which indicates withdrawal effects of the gadget. Though students felt well organized and well equipped with the latest knowledge as in Frequency table (2), more than 50%

stated depression which made them least interested in their studies as well as social interactions, Histogram (1). 59.6% felt poor sleep quality due to its undue use and this lack of sleep made their minds a center of fatigue and confusion, Histogram (2).

Increased incidence of headache was found in 61.8% of the students, Frequency table (3), and scientifically it has been approved to be a cause due to its "Blue light effect". Likewise, they were one of the causes of accidents with 62% votes, Pie graph (3). A source of attention diversion for about 75% of students was found as shown in Histogram (3).

More than 50% students used this as an excuse for not getting involved in conversations and thus have not been an active part of discussions, Frequency table (4). Most of the students thought that kids under 9 years of age should not be allowed to engage in the use of these smart devices, Bar chart (3) and about 72% wanted to restrict their daily phone usage to less than 2 hours a day, Pie graph (4).

So, the survey concluded that mobile phones no doubt were a huge source of education, communication, personal assistance and made many of us well organized but they have been a cause of distress. Lack of proper usage has led to many issues, worth concerned. Thus, their use should be regularized accordingly especially in the youngsters so that the youth may have the proper awareness of the beneficial effects of this gadget and the motive gets fulfilled for which mobile phones were actually made for.

TABLES AND GRAPHS:

FREQUENCY TABLE 1:

Benefit of use

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Entertainment	100	38.2	38.5	38.5
	Education	65	24.8	25.0	63.5
	Communication	75	28.6	28.8	92.3
	Personal Assistance	20	7.6	7.7	100.0
	Total	260	99.2	100.0	
Missing	System	2	.8		
	Total	262	100.0		

FREQUENCY TABLE 2:**Equipped with knowledge**

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	224	85.5	87.2	87.2
	No	33	12.6	12.8	100.0
	Total	257	98.1	100.0	
Missing	System	5	1.9		
	Total	262	100.0		

FREQUENCY TABLE 3:**Incidence of headache increased**

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	159	60.7	61.9	61.9
	No	98	37.4	38.1	100.0
	Total	257	98.1	100.0	
Missing	System	5	1.9		
	Total	262	100.0		

FREQUENCY TABLE 4:**Excuse to engage in conversation**

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	130	49.6	50.6	50.6
	No	127	48.5	49.4	100.0
	Total	257	98.1	100.0	
Missing	System	5	1.9		
	Total	262	100.0		

PIE GRAPH 1:
PIE GRAPH 2:

PIE GRAPH 3:

PIE GRAPH 4:

BAR GRAPH 1:

BAR GRAPH 2:

BAR GRAPH 3:

HISTOGRAM 1:

HISTOGRAM 2:

HISTOGRAM 3:**DISCUSSION:**

The aim of this report was to address the debilitating aspect of mobile phones and to assess the physical and mental issues regarding its addictive use as most of the times they are ignored because the spotlight is obviously on the other aspects like entertainment and social media indulging.

The study included students of all ages ranging from as low as 15 years to as high as 25 years however; the adult age group (ages 22-25) who were both physically and mentally stable comprised the principal population with 55.8% of the participation. About 60% of the participants have been using mobile phones for more than 5 years with about 3-5 hours daily usage showing that about 1/5th of daily routine includes mobile phones.

My concern about this is that entertainment was the major cause or role of its usage in the students surpassing the actual roles of communication and educational purposes which shows that the actual motive of this invention is somewhat lost. And my point is well validated by the with-drawl effects the students have without it. Depression was found in

about 50% of the subjects showing that psychological effects exist.

Lack of sleep in about 59.6% of the student was evident and with this the gadget has become a cause and center of fatigue and confusion due to the excessive use of mobile phones. Increased incidence of headache was found in 61.8% of the students and scientifically it has been approved to be a cause due to its "Blue light effect" well showing another truly bad biological effect of its use.

Likewise, they were one of the causes of accidents with 62% votes which is actually a concern in this regard as many of the people lose their lives in accidents annually. More than 75% of students are unable to concentrate on their works or tasks and find it difficult to concentrate because mobile phones have been named as the attention diversion cause by them. About 50% of them used this as an excuse for not been an active part of conversations and are actually socially less active and withdrawn. Most of the students thought that the kids under 9 years of age should not be given these devices and should not be allowed to engage in them. Also, they

think that this may cause an actual bad effect in their lives if they keep on using this in such an early age. About 72% of the participants want to regularize their use up to 2 hours a day which shows that they themselves feel that it is not been used well.

CONCLUSION:

Mobile phones addiction in modern era is real. The survey concluded that mobile phones no doubt, are a huge source of education, communication, personal assistance and made many of us well organized but they have been a cause of distress. Thus, their use should be regularized accordingly, especially in the youngsters

1. Knowledge needs to be provided to the youngsters about the stress and challenges they would face in the coming future if they not use the device well.
2. They need to be guided about how to cope with these challenges, when to ask for help and which rehab services they should contact if necessary.
3. The government should pay attention and conduct seminars and symposiums to let the generation get awareness about the things meant for.
4. Positive aspects and use of the mobile phones in the form of research or enlighten themselves with knowledge and guidance should be promoted.

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QUESTIONNAIRE:

Tick the options below.

1.What is your age?

- a)15-18 b) 18-21 c)22-25 d) 25 and above

2.How long have you been using a mobile phone?

- a)1-2 years b) 3-4years c) 4-5years d) More than 5 years

3.How many hours in a day do you spend using your phone?

- a)1hour b)2-3hours c) 3-5hours d) More than 6 hours

4.What is the benefit of using a phone (you can choose more than one option)

- a) Entertainment b) Education c) Communication d) Personal assistance

5.What phone would you prefer to buy and why?

- a) Expensive b) Low-priced c) Moderate priced d) I never buy one I use a hand me down

Why?

.....
.....

6.Would you feel uneasy if your phone was taken away from you?

- a) Yes b) No

7. What change in behavior have you noticed that resulted from your use of these electronic devices?

- a) Positive Change b) Negative Change

Starting from the positive

8.You are more organized?

- a) YES. b) NO.

9.You are well equipped with all the latest knowledge?

- a) YES. b) NO.

10. You are never bored?

- a) TRUE. b) FALSE.

.....
.....

Now for the negatives.

11. It creates a state of depression?

a) YES. b) NO.

12.I use it as an excuse to not engage in conversation or become more social?

a) Yes. b) NO

13.Poor sleep quality and quantity?

a) YES. b) NO.

14.A cause of accidents while driving?

a) YES. b) NO.

15.Attention diversion and sometimes not been able to focus on your daily tasks?

a) TRUE. b) FALSE.

16. Incidence of headache is increased?

a) YES. b) NO.

17.Do u seek approval from others on Social media in the form of likes or comments?

a) YES. b) NO.

18.Would u Allow kids Bellow the age of nine to use these smart devices?

a) YES. b) NO.

19. How often do you get distracted towards face book and what-s app while seeking for study stuff?

a) Usually. b) Rarely.

20. Do you prefer mobile phone usage over study in your free time?

a) Yes. b) No.

21. Would u bring about a restriction of its use to only 1-2 hours per day?

a) YES. b) NO.